

TripleVar: A Multimodal Deep Learning Framework for High-Fidelity Clinical Variant Effect Prediction in the Thiamine Transporter Genes SLC19A2 and SLC19A3

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Abstract

Background: Rapid and precise variant interpretation is critical for rare, treatable metabolic diseases where delayed diagnosis can lead to irreversible morbidity. Mutations in thiamine transporters SLC19A2 and SLC19A3 are linked to severe neurological disorders that are manageable with early intervention, yet over 470 variants of these genes in ClinVar remain variants of unknown significance (VUS), and more than 28,900 variants in dbSNP are entirely unclassified.

Goal and Methods: To develop a predictive model for accurate functional classification of genetic variants in the closely related thiamine transporter genes. We developed TripleVar, a multimodal deep learning model integrating DNABERT-2 genomic embeddings, ESM-2 protein embeddings, and allele frequency features for variant interpretation. This is the first end-to-end model combining these modalities. Training used 864 ClinVar variants (604 train, 130 validation, 130 test) in addition to 962 synthetic benign datapoints for contrastive learning. To assess generalization, we curated 20 experimentally validated SLC19A3 variants from the literature that are absent from ClinVar to serve as an independent validation test set

Results: On the ClinVar test set, TripleVar achieved a binary classification accuracy of 93.3% (benign vs. pathogenic) with a perfect AUC of 1.0 and 100% precision for pathogenic predictions. Including “likely-benign” and “likely-pathogenic” classes in the test, the model maintained 93.7% accuracy with a slight expected decrease of AUC to 0.913, reflecting their ambiguity. On the curated external set without allele frequency data, performance yielded 80% accuracy and 90% precision, demonstrating strong performance even when predictions rely solely on structural data. Applied to 28,925 unclassified variants and 470 VUS, TripleVar prioritized 111 high-confidence (0.37%) and 303 lower-confidence (1%) pathogenic candidates for follow-up.

Conclusions: TripleVar is a robust, clinically relevant predictor for SLC19A2/3 variant effects, demonstrating strong generalization beyond ClinVar. Ongoing HEK cell-based assays on randomly selected variants will further validate model predictions. This work establishes a scalable pipeline that can be applied to other genes, reducing VUS burden, accelerating rare disease diagnosis, and improving patient care.

TripleVar Multimodal Model Architecture

Figure 1: Model design integrating three input modalities: DNABERT-2 genomic embeddings, ESM-2 protein embeddings, and engineered tabular features (71D). The fused embedding ($\approx 6471D$) is processed through four dense layers and a softmax output layer predicting five clinical significance classes.

Figure 2: Comparison of TripleVar's classification performance across two datasets: the ClinVar test set (binary classification of pathogenic vs. benign variants) and a curated external dataset of experimentally validated SLC19A3 variants. Metrics include accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1-score, demonstrating strong model generalization even without allele frequency data.